

Pyridyl-imine-thioether complexes of ruthenium(II) : Synthesis, structure and optoelectronic and electron transfer properties[†]

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Abstract : Reactions of alkyl/aryl (2-pyridylimine)phenyl thioether (L^{SR}) with $RuCl_2(PPh_3)_3$ in ethanolic medium afford thioether complexes of type $[Ru(L^{SR})Cl(PPh_3)_2]PF_6$ ($R = \text{benzyl, phenyl}$). The ligands behave as tridentate neutral $N_{py}N_{imine}S_{thioether}$ donor retaining the C-S bond and bind to the metal atom in meridional fashion. The complexes were characterized by spectroscopic (IR, UV-Vis, and NMR) techniques. Crystallographic analysis reveals the octahedral geometry around ruthenium(II) with N_2SP_2Cl coordination. Complexes display rich optoelectronic features including luminescence. The complexes are electro-active and show quasi-reversible response near 1.1 V vs SCE. Theoretical (DFT) analyses were performed to explore the electronic transition and electron transfer behaviour.

Keywords : Ruthenium(II), C-S bond, thioether complex, crystal structure, metal redox, spectral properties, TD-DFT.

Introduction

The platinum-group-metals-sulfur chemistry is of intriguing interest because of the diversity in binding mode of sulfur atom with the metal¹. Notably, sulfur atom of the multidentate chelating agents can exhibit various coordination modes viz. thioether, thiolato, sulfenato as well as sulfinato². Ruthenium-sulfur compounds exhibit rich optoelectronic property including luminescence and this property has been suitably exploited in their applications as OLED³ apart from the use in solar energy converters⁴. Moreover, these complexes exhibit catalytic activity in various organic transformations⁵. From this perspective, the use of highly conjugated organic frameworks incorporating sulfur center can impart interesting physicochemical properties in their metallo-conjugates due to modifications of the FMOs.

In the recent past, we have reported the sulfur chemistry of rhodium(III) and iridium(III) with $C_{Ph}N_{azo}S$ coordinating ligands (Scheme 1), where the metal mediated C-S cleavage reaction has been scrutinized^{1a,c}. In the present work, we examine the coordinating behavior of the analogous ligand system viz. $N_{py}N_{imine}S$ (L^{SR}) donor (Scheme 1) toward $RuCl_2(PPh_3)_3$ and $RhCl_3/PPh_3$ and explore the feasibility of C-S cleavage reaction. We report the syn-

Scheme 1. Ligand frames containing $C_{Ph}N_{azo}S$ and $N_{py}N_{imine}S$ donors.

thesis, characterization along with the optoelectronic and electron transfer properties of a new set of ruthenocycle with tridentate neutral NNS ligands. It is worth noting that no C-S cleaved product has been found here in contrast with the aforesaid rhodium(III) and iridium(III) centers. Notably, thioether chemistry of ruthenium(II) complexes have been less explored relative to the analogous thiolato coordination⁶. The synthesized ruthenium(II) compounds are found to be stable in air and in presence of moisture. The geometry of the representative compounds has been authenticated by X-ray diffraction study. Finally, unification and correlation of spectral and electrochemical properties, structure and bonding are made with the aid of theoretical study.

[†]In honour of Professor Animesh Chakravorty on the occasion of his 80th birth anniversary.

Experimental

Materials :

2-Aminothiophenol, 2-pyridinecarboxaldehyde and triphenylphosphine were purchased from Aldrich Chemical Co., 2-(phenylthio)aniline from Fluka, $\text{RuCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ from Arora Matthey Ltd., benzyl chloride was purchased from Merck, India. All solvents were used as received. $\text{RuCl}_2(\text{PPh}_3)_3$ was synthesized following a reported procedure⁷.

Syntheses of ligands :

The ligands were synthesized by condensation of pyridine-2-carboxaldehyde with 2-(benzylthio)aniline **1a** and 2-(phenylthio)aniline **1b** in methanol.

Syntheses of complexes :

$[\text{Ru}(\text{L}^{\text{SCH}_2\text{Ph}})(\text{PPh}_3)_2\text{Cl}]\text{PF}_6$ (**2a**) : To an ethanolic solution of **1a** (32 mg, 0.105 mmol), 100 mg (0.104 mmol) of $\text{RuCl}_2(\text{PPh}_3)_3$ was added and the mixture was refluxed for 3 h. Excess NH_4PF_6 was added to the solution followed by stirring for 30 min. The resultant purple colored solution was evaporated under reduced pressure. Excess NH_4PF_6 was removed by thorough washing with water and the purple solid mass was dried in vacuum. The crude compound was subjected to column chromatography on a silica gel column. Pure compound was obtained as purple band with acetonitrile-toluene (1 : 3) solution as eluent. Yield : 75%. Anal. Calcd. (%) for $\text{C}_{55}\text{H}_{46}\text{N}_2\text{SClP}_3\text{F}_6\text{Ru}$: C, 59.49; H, 4.15; N, 2.52. Found : C, 59.38; H, 4.09; N, 2.48; FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 1601 $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$, 744, 694 and 519 $\nu_{\text{Rh-P}}$, 841 $\nu_{\text{P-F}}$; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 4.15 (d, 2J 10.8 Hz, CH_2Ph), 5.66 (d, 2J 10.8 Hz, CH_2Ph), 6.9–7.7 (2 PPh_3 and ligand Ph ring), 7.87 (d, 3J 6.4 Hz), 8.07 (d, 3J 6.9 Hz), 8.68 (d, 3J 5.0 Hz), 9.49 (s, imine CH); ^{31}P NMR (161.92 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 17.92 (s, PPh_3), –144.07 (septet, $^1J_{\text{P-F}}$ 725.4 Hz, PF_6^-).

$[\text{Ru}(\text{L}^{\text{SPh}})(\text{PPh}_3)_2\text{Cl}]\text{PF}_6$ (**2b**) : An analogous reaction was carried out with **1b** and $\text{RuCl}_2(\text{PPh}_3)_3$. Yield : 78%. Anal. Calcd. (%) for $\text{C}_{54}\text{H}_{44}\text{N}_2\text{SClP}_3\text{F}_6\text{Ru}$: C, 59.15; H, 4.02; N, 2.55. Found : C, 59.04; H, 4.05; N, 2.51; FT-IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 1602 $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$, 745, 696 and 520 $\nu_{\text{Rh-P}}$, 840 $\nu_{\text{P-F}}$; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 6.8–7.7 (2 PPh_3 and ligand Ph ring), 7.87 (d, 3J 6.5 Hz), 8.08 (d, 3J 7.0 Hz), 8.66 (d, 3J 5.0 Hz), 9.48 (s, imine CH); ^{31}P NMR (161.92 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 17.91 (s, PPh_3), –144.10 (septet, $^1J_{\text{P-F}}$ 725.2 Hz, PF_6^-).

Physical measurements :

^1H NMR spectral measurements were carried out on a Bruker FT 300 MHz spectrometer with TMS as an internal standard. ^{31}P NMR spectra were measured on a Bruker AMX 400 MHz spectrometer operating at 161.92 MHz. UV-Vis spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer LAMBDA 25 spectrophotometer. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer L-0100 spectrometer. The elemental analyses (C, H, N) were performed with a Perkin-Elmer model 2400 series II elemental analyzer. Room temperature emission spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer LS 55 Luminescence spectrometer. Electrochemical measurements were carried out at room temperature with VersaStat II Princeton Applied research potentiostat/galvanostat under argon atmosphere. The cell contained a Pt working electrode and a Pt wire auxiliary electrode. Tetraethylammonium perchlorate (NEt_4ClO_4) was used as supporting electrolyte and the potentials are referenced to the saturated calomel electrode (SCE) without junction correction.

Crystallographic details :

The single crystals suitable for X-Ray crystallographic analysis of complex **2b** was obtained by slow diffusion of dichloromethane solution of the complexes into hexane. Metal atoms were located by direct methods, and the rest of the non-hydrogen atoms emerged from successive Fourier synthesis. The structures were refined by full-matrix least squares procedure on F^2 . All non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically. All the hydrogen atoms were included in calculated positions and were treated as riding atoms using SHELXL default parameters. Metal atoms were located and solved by direct methods using the program SHELXS-97⁸. The refinement and all further calculations were carried out using SHELXL-97⁹. Calculations were performed using the SHELXTL v.6.14 program package¹⁰. Molecular structure plots were drawn using ORTEP¹¹ and thermal ellipsoids were drawn at the 35% probability level.

Computational details :

The molecular geometries of the singlet ground state (S_0) of the synthesized complex **2a** has been calculated by the DFT method¹² using the (R)B3LYP¹³ hybrid functional approach incorporated into the GAUSSIAN 09 pro-

gram package¹⁴. The geometries of the complexes were fully optimized in the gas phase without any ligand simplification using its crystallographic coordinates. The optimized structural parameters are in general good agreement with the experimental values and the slight discrepancy arises due to the distortion in the crystal lattice that exists in real molecules. The nature of all the stationary points was checked by computing vibration frequencies, and all the species were found to be true potential energy minima, as no imaginary frequency were obtained (NImag = 0). On the basis of the optimized geometries, the absorption spectral properties in dichloromethane (CH₂Cl₂) media were calculated by the time-dependent density functional theory (TD-DFT)¹⁵ approach associated with the conductor-like polarizable continuum model (CPCM)¹⁶. We computed the lowest 100 singlet-singlet transitions in absorption and the results of the TD calculations were qualitatively similar to the observed spectra. The TD-DFT approach is now well-known as a rigorous formalism for the treatment of electronic excitation energies within the DFT framework for calculating spectral properties of many transition metal complexes¹⁷. To analyze the nature of absorption and emission processes, natural transition orbital (NTO) analysis were performed¹⁸. This method offers the most compact representation of the transition density between the ground and excited states in terms of an expansion into single-particle transitions (hole and electron states for each given excitation). Here we refer to the unoccupied and occupied NTOs as “electron” and “hole” transition orbitals. The computed vertical transitions were calculated at the equilibrium geometry of the *S*₀ state and described in terms of one-electron excitations of molecular orbitals of the corresponding *S*₀ geometry. The calculated transitions with moderate intensities (*f* ≥ 0.02) can be envisaged going from the lower to the higher energy region of the spectrum. The iridium atom was described by a double- ζ basis set with the effective core potential of Hay and Wadt (LANL2DZ)¹⁹ and the 6-31G basis set²⁰ was used for the other elements except S, P and Cl atom (6-31+G(d,p)) present in the complexes to optimize the ground state geometries. The calculated electronic density plots for frontier molecular orbitals were prepared by using the GaussView 5.0 software. GaussSum program, version 2.2²¹ was used to calculate the molecular orbital contributions from groups or atoms.

Results and discussion

Synthesis :

Treatment of an ethanolic solution of RuCl₂(PPh₃)₃ with L^{SR} (**1a**, R = benzyl; **1b**, R = phenyl) under refluxing condition has afforded [Ru(L^{SR})Cl(PPh₃)₂]⁺PF₆⁻ **2** as the purple solid in good yield (Scheme 2). The ligands behave as tridentate neutral *N*_{py}*N*_{imine}*S*_{thioether} donor. Sulfur atom is coordinated as thioether mode with the retention of the C-S bond in the course of the reaction. After completion of the reaction, NH₄PF₆ was added to satisfy the primary valence of ruthenium(II).

Scheme 2. Reaction of RuCl₂(PPh₃)₃ with **1**.

Significantly, no C-S cleavage product has been found during the reaction of RuCl₂(PPh₃)₃ with **1**. Moreover, the thioether complexes **2** have also been observed as the sole product when RuCl₃ was treated with **1** in presence of excess PPh₃. We have recently reported that the reactions of M^{III} (M = Rh, Ir) with superior π -acidic thioether ligands furnished thiolato complexes via *in situ* C-S scission^{1a,c}. The apparent disparity can be attributed to the inaccessibility of the *meta*-stable lower valence intermediate, Ru^I species, in the present coordinating environment with Schiff base. It has been found that the stability of lower valence state of metal (here Ru^I) in due course of the reaction is a prerequisite for C-S bond breaking leading to thiolato coordination^{1a,c}. However, we anticipate that ruthenium(II) thiolato complexes can be formed if enough π -acidic environment is provided around the metal atom.

Notably, analogous reaction in non-polar benzene solvent afforded neutral thioether complexes of type [Ru(L^{SR})Cl₂(PPh₃)]⁰^{6b}. In this work, we used polar ethanol as solvent and obtained the red-purple cationic complexes containing two PPh₃ molecules and one Cl as coligands. Thus solvent plays a significant role in this reaction i.e. more polar solvent facilitates the formation of cationic complex.

*Spectral studies :**IR spectra :*

Infrared spectra of the complexes **2a** and **2b** exhibit many sharp and strong vibrations within 1700–400 cm^{-1} . In the spectra of the free ligands, sharp strong bands appeared near 1620 cm^{-1} is due to aldimine (C=N) stretching mode of the ligand which are shifted bathochromically (red shift) to around 1600 cm^{-1} on complexation. This suggests coordination of the metal ions to the azomethine nitrogen²². IR spectra of the complexes show three sharp peaks near 520 cm^{-1} , 700 cm^{-1} and 745 cm^{-1} . These peaks confirm the presence of two PPh_3 groups *trans* to each other as similar *trans*-M (PPh_3)₂ fragments are known to display such vibrations^{1a,c}. The strong peak at 840 cm^{-1} is attributed to the $\nu_{\text{P-F}}$ stretching which clearly indicates the presence of PF_6^- as counter anion.

¹H NMR spectra :

The synthesized complexes are diamagnetic, which corresponds to presence of ruthenium(II) (low-spin d^6 , $S = 0$) in these complexes. ¹H NMR of the free ligands show sharp singlet near 8.5 ppm due to aldimine proton which has been shifted downfield to near 9.5 ppm in the complexes. The downfield shift reveals the coordination of imine nitrogen to the metal centre²³. The sharp singlet at 4.18 ppm in the spectrum of **1a** is due to S-CH₂Ph protons which in spectrum of the complex **2a** is split into two distinct doublets ($^2J_{\text{H-H}} = 11$ Hz) at 4.16 ppm and 5.70 ppm with a separation of ~ 1.5 ppm. This is attributed to the nonequivalent nature of the S-CH₂Ph protons in the complexes^{1a,c,24}. This feature ascertains the coordination through thioether S atom retaining the benzyl group. Remaining ligand protons as well as phosphine protons are observed in the range of 6.5 to 8.5 ppm in both the complexes. The coordinating ligands L^{SR} act as neutral tridentate NNS donors during complexation with ruthenium(II). The ¹H NMR spectra of **2a** and **2b** show 1 : 2 intensity ratio of ligand/triphenylphosphine signals, corresponding to ruthenium(II) hexacoordinated species with two PPh_3 molecules.

³¹P NMR spectra :

The ³¹P NMR spectra in CDCl_3 of both the complexes exhibit one singlet resonance near 17.9 ppm, indicating equivalent phosphine environment i.e. *trans* dispositions of PPh_3 groups in the compounds (Fig. 1). A septet pattern is also observed around -150 ppm due to the spin-spin coupling of the ¹⁹F nucleus ($I = 1/2$) with the ³¹P nucleus, reflecting the presence of PF_6^- as counter anion (inset of Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. ³¹P NMR spectra of cationic complex **2a** (counter anion PF_6^- in the inset).

UV-Vis spectra :

Electronic spectra of the complexes (Fig. 2, Table 1) exhibit multiple transitions and these excitations are attributed primarily to the charge-transfer in nature. To understand optical absorption processes in details, we performed theoretical (TD-DFT and NTO) analyses. The most relevant transitions and NTOs for **2b** are listed in Table 2 and Fig. 3.

For **2b**, lower energy transition around 484 nm is computed at 493 nm (2.2431 eV, $f = 0.0303$) as the $\{4d_{\text{zx}}(\text{Ru}) + 3p(\text{S} + \text{Cl})\} \rightarrow \{\pi^*(\text{imine} + \text{Ph}) + 4d_{\text{yz}}(\text{Ru})\}$ MLCT transition admixed with LLCT character. The transition near 432 nm (3.4789 eV, $f = 0.0614$, $\lambda_{\text{theo}} = 356$ nm) can be attributed as $\{4d_{\text{zx}}(\text{Ru}) + 3p(\text{S} + \text{Cl})\} \rightarrow \{\pi^*(\text{imine} + \text{Ph}) + 4d_{\text{yz}}(\text{Ru})\}$ MLCT transition slightly mixed with LLCT character. UV transition at 290 nm is computed at

Fig. 2. UV-Vis spectra of complexes; **2a** (dashed) and **2b** (line).

Table 1. UV-Vis, emission spectral and cyclic voltammetric data

Compound	UV-Vis data ^a	Emission	Quantum	Cyclic
	λ_{\max} (nm) (ϵ , M ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	spectral data ^b λ_{\max} (nm)	yield (Φ) ^c	voltammetric data ^d (V)
[Ru(L ^{SCH₂Ph})Cl(PPh ₃) ₂]PF ₆	500(3300), 364(8200)sh, 316(16450)	470	4.7×10^{-4}	1.12
[Ru(L ^{SPh})Cl(PPh ₃) ₂]PF ₆	516(2900), 340(10900)sh, 296(16100)	473	6.4×10^{-3}	1.15

^aIn acetonitrile. ^bIn acetonitrile, excitation at 296 nm. ^cIn deoxygenated acetonitrile. ^dSolvent, acetonitrile; supporting electrolyte, TEAP; reference electrode SCE; scan rate, 50 mV/s⁻¹.

Table 2. Main optical transition at the TD-DFT/B3LYP level for the complex **2b** with composition in terms of molecular orbital contribution of the transition, computed vertical excitation energies, and oscillator strength in acetonitrile

Transition	CI	Composition	<i>E</i> (eV)	Oscillator strength (<i>f</i>)	λ_{theo} (nm)
$S_0 \rightarrow S_3$	0.58483	H-2- > LUMO (68%)	2.5131	0.0303	493.35
	-0.29904	H-1- > LUMO (18%)			
$S_0 \rightarrow S_{13}$	0.61556	H-2- > LUMO (76%)	3.4789	0.0614	356.39
$S_0 \rightarrow S_{30}$	0.62747	HOMO- > L+4 (79%)	4.1331	0.0428	299.98

Fig. 3. Natural transition orbitals (NTOs) for complex **2b** illustrating the nature of singlet excited states in the absorption bands in the range 290–550 nm. For each state, the respective number of the state, transition energy (eV), and the oscillator strength (in parentheses) are listed. Only occupied (holes) and unoccupied (electrons) NTO pairs that contribute more than 60% to each excited state are shown.

300 nm (4.1331 eV, $f = 0.0428$) and can be ascribed exclusively as $\{4d_{yz}(\text{Ru}) + 3p(\text{S} + \text{Cl}) \rightarrow \pi^*(\text{Ph})\}$ MLCT transitions with significant mixing of LLCT nature.

Emission spectra :

The complexes show weak blue luminescence in acetonitrile solution with a broad emission band centered

around $\lambda = 470$ nm after excitation at $\lambda = 296$ nm (Fig. 4). Complex **2a** is even more weakly emissive than **2b**. Platinum-group metals-phosphine complexes rarely show emissive property at room temperature²⁵. Emission quantum yields were determined at 25 °C in deoxygenated acetonitrile solution (argon bubbling for 30 min) with an-

Fig. 4. Emission spectrum of **2b**.

thracene in ethanol as standard ($\Phi_r = 0.27$)²⁶. The emission quantum yield for complexes (Φ_u) was calculated by the well-known equation given below :

$$\Phi_u = \Phi_r(A_r/A_u)(I_u/I_r)(n_u/n_r)^2$$

where A_u , A_r are the absorption values of unknown and reference; I_u , I_r are the integrated emission areas of unknown and reference; and n_u , n_r are the refractive indices of the solvents containing unknown and reference²⁷. The emission and quantum yield data are given in Table 1.

Rigid structure of the molecule favors luminescence²⁸. Complex with S-phenyl ligand assumes more rigid structure as compared to S-benzyl ligand and this is probably the reason for stronger emissive nature of the former. Disparity in emissive properties of **2a** and **2b** is an indication of ligand centered nature of the observed emission.

Crystal structure :

The X-ray crystal structure of a representative complex **2b** (R = Ph) was determined to establish the geometry about the metal ions as well as the bonding modes of the Schiff base ligand and the coligands. The ORTEP and atom numbering scheme of the complex **2b** are shown in Fig. 5. Selected metrical parameters and crystallographic details for the complex **2b** are given in Tables 3 and 4 respectively.

Single crystals of the complex **2b** suitable for X-ray analysis were grown by slow diffusion of hexane into dichloromethane solution at room temperature. The compound crystallizes in monoclinic space group $P2_1/n$. Crystallographic analysis of the thioether complex reveals that phenyl 2-(2-pyridylazomethine)phenyl thioether (L^{SPh})

Fig. 5. ORTEP of **2b** (H atoms, solvate and counter anion are omitted for clarity).Table 3. Selected metrical parameters for **2b**.CH₂Cl₂

Bond length (Å)			
Ru1-N1	2.091(4)	Ru1-S1	2.349(2)
Ru1-N2	2.015(4)	C6-N2	1.296(7)
Ru1-P1	2.422(2)	C12-S1	1.779(6)
Ru1-P2	2.421(2)	C13-S1	1.797(6)
Ru1-Cl1	2.436(1)		
Bond angles (°)			
N1-Ru1-N2	78.66(17)	P1-Ru1-P2	173.66(5)
N2-Ru1-S1	82.97(13)	C12-S1-C13	101.16(3)

ligand is coordinated as a neutral tridentate N,N,S donor forming two contiguous five-membered chelate rings. The NNS coordinating ligand, Cl atom and metal center constitute the equatorial plane, while the two PPh₃ molecules occupy mutually *trans* positions. The N₂SP₂Cl coordination sphere around ruthenium is distorted octahedral in nature. The complex as a whole is monocationic, and the crystallographic asymmetric unit contains a PF₆⁻ as counter anion and also dichloromethane as solvate.

Bond length values reveal that Ru-N_{imine} bond length (2.015 Å) is considerably shorter by *ca.* 0.08 Å than Ru-N_{py} bond length (2.091 Å). This indicates partial double bond character of Ru-N_{imine} bond due to appreciable Rh(*t*₂)

Table 4. Crystallographic parameters of **2b**.CH₂Cl₂

Parameters	2b .CH ₂ Cl ₂
Empirical formula	[C ₅₄ H ₄₄ N ₂ P ₂ SClRu] ⁺ (PF ₆) ⁻ .CH ₂ Cl ₂
Formula weight	1181.34
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Space group	<i>P</i> 2 ₁ / <i>n</i>
<i>a</i> (Å)	16.776(3)
<i>b</i> (Å)	16.398(3)
<i>c</i> (Å)	19.779(4)
α (°)	90.00
β (°)	102.86(3)
γ (°)	90.00
<i>Z</i>	4
<i>D</i> _{calcd} (g cm ⁻³)	1.479
μ (mm ⁻¹)	0.637
<i>F</i> (000)	2400
θ Range (°)	1.63–25.00
Measured reflections	37510
Unique reflections (<i>R</i> _{int})	9332 (0.0498)
<i>R</i> [<i>I</i> > 2σ(<i>I</i>)] <i>R</i> 1 ^{<i>a</i>} , w <i>R</i> 2 ^{<i>b</i>}	0.0714, 0.1575
<i>R</i> (all data) <i>R</i> 1, w <i>R</i> 2	0.0882, 0.1662
Goodness-of-fit on <i>F</i> ²	1.169
Largest diff. in peak and hole (e Å ⁻³)	0.962 and -0.632
CCDC No.	1434425
^{<i>a</i>} <i>R</i> 1 = Σ <i>F</i> _o - <i>F</i> _c /Σ <i>F</i> _o . ^{<i>b</i>} w <i>R</i> 2 = [Σw(<i>F</i> _o ² - <i>F</i> _c ²)/Σw(<i>F</i> _o ²)] ^{1/2} .	

→ N_{imine}(π*) back bonding^{1c}. However, the effect of such back donation is rather diminutive on the imine (>C=N-) bond length since the C-N length (1.296 Å) in **2b** is marginally elongated compared with that in free ligands (1.28 Å)²⁹.

Electrochemical studies :

The complexes are electro-active in acetonitrile solution. They exhibit quasi-reversible one-electron oxidative response with *E*_{1/2} = 1.15 V referenced to Saturated Calomel Electrode (Fig. 6, Table 1). This response is believed to be of Ru^{II}-Ru^{III} redox couple (Scheme 3)³⁰.

Scheme 3. Electrochemical oxidation of complex.

The peak separations are slightly higher (Δ*H*_{pp} = 100 mV) than ideal value of 59 mV, but they are common for this type of complexes³¹. Nature of redox couple signifies that ruthenium(III) can also be stabilized in N₂P₂SCl coor-

Fig. 6. Cyclic voltammogram of **2b** in acetonitrile.

dinating environment.

Frontier Molecular Orbitals :

To gain insight into the nature of FMOs, we performed Density Functional Theory (DFT) calculations with the crystallographic parameters. The isodensity plots from HOMO-2 to LUMO+2 for **2b** are illustrated in Fig. 7 and compositions of frontier molecular orbitals are given in Table 5. DFT calculations show that HOMO and HOMO-1 have major contribution from metal (53% and 47% for HOMO and HOMO-1 respectively) with negligible contribution from ligand. LUMO is predominantly centered on the imine bond and pyridine ring of Schiff base ligand. During oxidation electron is released from

Fig. 7. Selected FMOs of **2b**.

Table 5. Compositions (%) of Frontier Molecular Orbitals of complex **2b**

MO	Energy (eV)	Contribution (%)						
		Ru	Ligand				PPh ₃ + Cl	Main Bond Type
			py	imine	aryl	SPh		
L+4	-3.24	21	4	3	20	38	15	$\pi^*(L) + d(Ru) + \pi(PPh_3)$
L+3	-3.28	16	2	2	57	12	12	$\pi^*(L) + \pi(PPh_3)$
L+2	-3.64	26	29	1	1	8	35	$\pi^*(L) + d(Ru) + \pi(PPh_3)$
L+1	-3.66	13	63	1	3	6	14	$\pi^*(L)$
LUMO	-5.25	10	34	36	17	1	2	$\pi^*(L)$
HOMO	-7.86	53	4	4	2	8	30	$d(Ru) + \pi(Cl)$
H-1	-7.97	47	3	4	1	4	42	$d(Ru) + \pi(Cl)$
H-2	-8.31	24	2	2	3	9	59	$\pi(PPh_3) + d(Ru)$
H-3	-8.43	51	9	2	2	5	32	$d(Ru) + \pi(PPh_3)$
H-4	-8.68	3	2	1	1	2	91	$\pi(PPh_3)$

HOMO of the complex, hence oxidative response in cyclic voltammetry is assigned to be metal centered involving oxidation of Ru^{II} to Ru^{III}.

Conclusion

In this work, a convenient synthesis of mononuclear Ru^{II} thioether complexes with azomethine function along with pyridyl-N and thioether-S are described. The reported ligands behave as tridentate neutral $N_{py}N_{im}S_{thioether}$ donor and exhibit strong affinity toward Ru^{II}, indicating their overall soft nature. Formation of exclusive thioether complexes even in the presence of excess phosphine is an indicative of the inferior π -acidic nature of these chelating agents vis-à-vis inaccessibility of unstable Ru^I intermediate in the reaction coordinates. We anticipate that the thiolate complexes of Ru^{II} would be the end products with the superior π -acceptor ligands under similar reaction conditions. Accordingly, the azomethine function plays an important role to terminate the reaction with the thioether compounds. These complexes exhibit rich optoelectronic features and the excitations are assigned primarily as MLCT transitions based on TD-DFT and NTO analyses. The oxidative response is attributed to the metal-centered redox process (Ru^{II} \rightarrow Ru^{III}) and consistent with the nature of HOMO, 53% of d_{Ru} . The complexes are weakly blue emissive in nature.

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Supplementary data

Crystallographic data of the Ru^{II} complex (**2b**) has been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Center, CCDC number 1434425.

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